

Mass Media and Community Development: A Stakeholders' Engagement Approach in Rivers State, Nigeria

Lebari-Nbarawii Victoria, Sarah Chidiebere Joe & Njoku Justice

Department of Mass Communication,
Faculty of Communication and Media Studies
Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

Abstract

This study investigated the influence of mass media in community empowerment through stakeholders' engagement in Rivers State, Nigeria. Anchored on Participatory Communication Theory and Stakeholders Theory, the study examined how mass media facilitate community development, the extent of stakeholder engagement in planning and implementation of media-based development efforts, and the challenges thereof. A survey research design was adopted with a population of 4,542,673 Rivers State residents. Using the Taro Yamane formula, a sample of 400 respondents was drawn via multi-stage sampling, and 385 questionnaires were successfully retrieved. A 4-point Likert-scale Weighted Mean Score was used for analysis, supplemented by qualitative interviews with community leaders. Findings revealed that mass media play essential roles in promoting community development through citizens' engagement and agenda-setting strategies. Stakeholders are incorporated in project planning, while social media platforms have significantly boosted community mobilisation. Key challenges include illiteracy, media ownership patterns, and the uneven inclusion of local stakeholders in project execution. The study recommends that community-based projects be prioritised in media schedules, stakeholders be empowered to monitor rural projects, and that new media platforms be systematically utilised for inclusive community development in Rivers State.

Keywords: *mass media, community development, stakeholders' engagement, participatory communication, Rivers State, social media, rural empowerment*

INTRODUCTION

The role of mass media organisations in information gathering, gatekeeping, and dissemination occupies a central position in contemporary democratic societies. More significant is their advocacy function in facilitating citizen engagements and community development programmes through stakeholder relations and involvement in community projects. Over the years, mass media — both print and electronic — have served as the watchdog of society, providing surveillance of government policies, particularly as these concerns the welfare of communities across Nigeria (Kobani & Alozie, 2019).

Community development, as defined by the Cambridge Summer Conference (1948), is a movement designed to promote better living with the active participation of the community, and where such initiative is absent, by using techniques to arouse and stimulate it in order to ensure active and enthusiastic response. This definition underscores the importance of stakeholders' participation in drafting and executing community-based projects. The media, through advocacy roles, draws the attention of both stakeholders and government toward projects that would benefit the people.

The proliferation of mass media organisations has made it considerably easier for members of local communities to access media platforms, especially radio, which has the capacity to reach governments, interest groups, and organisations at various community levels. The influence which the media exerts through agenda-setting, priming, framing strategies, and advocacy roles has helped tremendously in empowering and getting members of local communities to participate in policies and programmes that benefit them.

Notably, social media platforms — including WhatsApp groups, Facebook pages, Telegram groups, Twitter/X handles, and YouTube channels — have emerged as veritable tools for improving communication and information sharing among communities, as well as for discussing and addressing issues that affect local populations. Members of local communities have leveraged these new media platforms to encourage social relationships and community resource control (Mzizi & Govender, 2024).

However, despite the acknowledged importance of media-stakeholder synergy in driving community development, empirical studies examining this dynamic specifically within Rivers State are limited. Most existing research has focused on media coverage patterns (Okhegwae et al., 2018), television's developmental role (Shitak, 2011), or broad national-level strategies (Uche & Ukaegbu, 2021), without adequately situating the Rivers State context or integrating the multi-platform, multi-stakeholder approach. This study fills this gap by empirically investigating the influence of mass media in community empowerment through stakeholders' engagement in Rivers State.

Research Objectives

The specific objectives of this study were to: (i) examine the roles mass media play in promoting community development in Rivers State; (ii) determine how stakeholders are engaged in the planning and implementation of media-based development efforts; (iii) identify the challenges of stakeholder engagement in media-led development; and (iv) ascertain the manner in which interest groups utilise new media platforms to influence government policies on community-based projects.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Mass Media as a Tool for Community Development

Mass media encompasses the collective communication channels that simultaneously reach large and dispersed audiences. These include newspapers, radio, television, the internet, and social media platforms (Aggarwal & Gupta, 2001). For developing nations like Nigeria, mass media has served not only as an entertainment and information vehicle but as a fundamental instrument for social mobilisation and community advancement.

Newspaper, as the oldest and most enduring print medium, retains a significant role in highlighting community issues and setting the public agenda (Okhegwae et al., 2018). Studies have shown that national dailies in Nigeria, however, frequently give disproportionate prominence to national over community-level issues, effectively marginalising grassroots voices (Okhegwae et al., 2018). Radio, given its wide reach and oral accessibility, is particularly impactful in rural communities where literacy rates are lower. The medium's capacity to engage diverse linguistic and educational demographics makes it a powerful tool for mobilising rural stakeholders and generating civic participation (Apuke, 2017).

Television has evolved from being perceived as an entertainment medium to a powerful instrument for public enlightenment, development communication, and even community advancement. Adesina et al. (2017) note that television permeates both urban and rural homes, providing education, news, and entertainment, and influencing cultural attitudes. Sharma (2018) reinforces this view, noting that television shapes the behaviours and cultural orientations of its audiences, making it a critical platform for community sensitisation and development messaging.

The emergence of new media — particularly social media — has dramatically altered the landscape of community engagement and development communication. Vinay (2022) demonstrated that social media has become an indispensable tool for community developers, facilitating resource mobilisation and broad-based information dissemination. Similarly, Mzizi and Govender (2024) found that while social media is widely perceived as an effective communication tool for stakeholder engagement, poor utilisation levels persist in many organisations, calling for training and strategic social media policies.

Stakeholders' Engagement in Community Development

Stakeholder theory, originally proposed by Carroll (1979) and expanded by Freeman (1984), posits that organisations must consider the interests and participation of all groups who are affected by or can affect their operations. In the context of community development, stakeholders include government agencies, non-governmental organisations, traditional rulers, community leaders, youth groups, women's associations, and media practitioners.

Laetitia and Amolo (2025), in their study conducted in Rwanda, demonstrated that stakeholder empowerment strategies — including capacity building, seed capital, and social networking — significantly influence the performance of community development projects. Their study found that entrepreneurial capacity building had a significant positive effect ($p=0.000$) on project performance, illustrating that the integration of local stakeholders is not merely procedural but fundamentally impacts development outcomes.

In Rivers State, Kobani and Johnbull (2019) found that mass media play critical roles in community development programmes in Akuku-Toru, mediating between communities and government institutions. Their study showed that media organisations serve as conduits for community grievances, advocates for project execution, and platforms for celebrating community achievements. The present study extends this line of inquiry by examining the specific mechanisms through which stakeholder engagement, mediated by mass media, translates into tangible community development outcomes.

Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in two complementary theoretical frameworks: Participatory Communication Theory and Stakeholders Theory. Participatory Communication Theory, championed by Quebral (1972, 1975, 2001, 2007) in the context of development communication, emphasises the importance of horizontal, dialogic communication that

empowers communities to participate actively in decisions that affect them. Rather than treating communities as passive recipients of top-down messages, this theory advocates for inclusive communication strategies that amplify local voices and facilitate genuine engagement.

Stakeholders Theory, originally a framework for corporate governance, has been adapted extensively in development communication to underscore the vital role of all interest groups in community projects. Carroll (1991, 1999) and Fombrun et al. (2000) argue that neglecting stakeholders' interests not only undermines project legitimacy but also risks conflict and project failure. In the community development context, this theory explains why the media must facilitate stakeholders' recognition, representation, and meaningful participation in project planning, execution, and monitoring.

Together, these two frameworks provide a robust basis for understanding how mass media can serve as the bridge between communities and governance institutions, fostering inclusive development through systematic stakeholder engagement.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study adopted a mixed-methods research design, combining a quantitative survey with qualitative interviews. The survey design was selected for its effectiveness in assessing the attitudes and opinions of a large, geographically distributed population. The qualitative interview component allowed the researcher to gather in-depth perspectives from community leaders and stakeholders on the nuanced realities of media-facilitated community development.

Population and Sample Size

The population comprised all Rivers State residents, projected at 4,542,673 based on the 2006 National Population Census figure of 3,187,841, extrapolated at a growth rate of 2.5% to 2025. The sample size was determined using the Taro Yamane (1967) formula:

$$n = N / [1 + N(e)^2]$$

Where n = sample size, N = total population (4,542,673), and e = acceptable error margin (0.05). This yielded $n \approx 400$ respondents.

Sampling Technique

A multi-stage sampling technique was employed. At the first stage, Rivers State was divided into three Senatorial Zones; Rivers East and Rivers South-East were selected for accessibility. At the second stage, six Local Government Areas (LGAs) were selected — Obio/Akpor, Ikwerre, and Omuna from Rivers East; and Tai, Oyigbo, and Eleme from Rivers South-East. At the third stage, 40 wards (out of 70) were selected from these six LGAs, yielding 100 communities. Three respondents were selected per community, administered at intervals of every five households, resulting in the target sample of 400. A total of 385 questionnaires were successfully retrieved, accounting for attrition.

Data Collection and Analysis

The primary data collection instrument was a structured questionnaire divided into two sections: Section A captured respondents' demographic data (gender, age, marital status, educational qualification), while Section B contained psychographic items designed around the four research questions, using a 4-point Likert scale (Strongly Agree = 4, Agree = 3, Disagree = 2, Strongly Disagree = 1). A Weighted Mean Score (WMS) was used for analysis; items with $WMS \geq 2.5$ were accepted, and those below were rejected. Qualitative data were gathered through structured interviews with community leaders and analysed thematically. Validity was established through expert review by supervisors and communication scholars, while reliability was assessed using the test-retest method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Profile of Respondents

Of the 385 respondents, 203 (52.7%) were male and 182 (47.3%) were female, suggesting a near-equal gender representation. The majority (34.5%) fell within the 28–37 age bracket, with a significant portion (29.1%) aged 38–47. In terms of educational qualification, 41.8% held a B.Sc. or its equivalent, indicating a largely literate and educated sample, though diversity across educational levels was maintained through multi-stage sampling.

Research Question One: Roles of Mass Media in Promoting Community Development

Respondents overwhelmingly affirmed the essential roles of mass media in promoting community development. Table 1 summarises the findings for the three items under this research question.

Table 1: Mass Media Roles in Community Development

Statement	SA (n)	A (n)	D (n)	WMS
Mass media play essential roles in community development	218	119	48	3.5 ✓
Agenda-setting promotes rural community empowerment	195	132	58	3.2 ✓
Opinion leaders leverage media to demand government intervention	207	126	52	3.4 ✓

SA = Strongly Agree; A = Agree; D = Disagree/Strongly Disagree; WMS = Weighted Mean Score; ✓ = Accepted (WMS ≥ 2.5)

Findings indicate that a majority of respondents strongly agreed that mass media play essential roles in promoting community development involving citizens' engagement (WMS = 3.5). Respondents also affirmed that media agenda-setting strategies meaningfully promote community empowerment (WMS = 3.2), and that opinion leaders leverage various media outlets to advocate for government intervention on behalf of rural dwellers (WMS = 3.4). These findings align with Kobani and Johnbull (2019), who documented the intermediary role of media in connecting rural communities with government institutions in Rivers State.

Research Question Two: Stakeholder Engagement in Planning and Implementation

The second research question explored whether community-based stakeholders are meaningfully incorporated in the planning and implementation of development projects. Table 2 presents the results.

Table 2: Stakeholder Engagement in Project Planning and Implementation

Statement	SA (n)	A (n)	D (n)	WMS
Stakeholders incorporated in planning & implementation of projects	213	108	64	3.4 ✓
Culture and traditions affect community project execution	198	121	66	3.2 ✓
Stakeholders act as subcontractors in rural project execution	176	130	79	3.1 ✓

SA = Strongly Agree; A = Agree; D = Disagree/Strongly Disagree; WMS = Weighted Mean Score; ✓ = Accepted (WMS ≥ 2.5)

Results show that a majority of respondents strongly agreed that community-based stakeholders are incorporated in the planning and implementation of projects (WMS = 3.4). Respondents also affirmed that cultural and traditional values affect the execution of community-based projects (WMS = 3.2), and that stakeholders frequently serve as subcontractors in rural project execution (WMS = 3.1). Qualitative interviews corroborated these findings. A community leader from Eligbolo community noted that while stakeholder consultation occurs for some projects, it is inconsistently applied: 'In some projects, we are contacted and made to take part in decision making, while in some other regards, you just see contracts and government personnel.' This points to the need for institutionalising stakeholder engagement protocols in Rivers State development practice.

Research Question Three: Challenges of Stakeholder Engagement in Media-Led Development

Table 3 presents findings on the challenges associated with stakeholder engagement in media-led community development.

Table 3: Challenges of Stakeholder Engagement in Media-Led Development

Statement	SA (n)	A (n)	D (n)	WMS
Ignorance and illiteracy are impediments to media-stakeholder engagement	209	105	71	3.4 ✓
Media ownership patterns constrain community project mobilisation	219	71	95	3.7 ✓
Government policies are impediments to community project awareness	97	54	234	2.2 ✗

SA = Strongly Agree; A = Agree; D = Disagree/Strongly Disagree; WMS = Weighted Mean Score; ✓ = Accepted; ✗ = Rejected

Findings reveal that ignorance and illiteracy constitute significant impediments to the incorporation of rural stakeholders in media-mediated development (WMS = 3.4). This is consistent with literacy challenges documented across rural Nigeria, where low educational attainment limits communities' ability to engage with print and digital media platforms. Media ownership and control patterns were identified as even more significant constraints (WMS = 3.7), corroborating concerns raised by Okhegwae et al. (2018) about the urban-centric bias of Nigeria's mainstream media. Notably, government policies were not perceived as significant barriers to community project awareness (WMS = 2.2, Rejected), suggesting that the major constraints are structural and capacity-related rather than regulatory.

Research Question Four: New Media Platforms and Government Policy Influence

The fourth research question examined the manner in which interest groups utilise new media platforms to influence government policies on community-based projects. Table 4 presents the findings.

Table 4: New Media Platforms and Community Mobilisation

Statement	SA (n)	A (n)	D (n)	WMS
Social media groups have boosted community empowerment mobilisation	210	120	55	3.5 ✓
New media creates more influence for government intervention in projects	156	130	99	3.0 ✓
Media and rural stakeholders use social media in project planning	213	113	59	3.4 ✓

SA = Strongly Agree; A = Agree; D = Disagree/Strongly Disagree; WMS = Weighted Mean Score; ✓ = Accepted (WMS ≥ 2.5)

Findings confirm that social media platforms have significantly boosted the mobilisation of local dwellers for community empowerment (WMS = 3.5). The use of platforms such as WhatsApp, Facebook, and Telegram groups by community members — particularly those in the diaspora — has enabled coordinated advocacy, fundraising, and project monitoring. Respondents also affirmed that new media platforms create greater influence in drawing government attention to community needs (WMS = 3.0), and that both media practitioners and rural stakeholders actively utilise social media in the planning and execution of community-based projects (WMS = 3.4). These results align strongly with Vinay (2022) and Mzizi and Govender (2024), who demonstrated the transformative potential of social media for inclusive development communication.

DISCUSSION

The collective findings of this study paint a compelling picture of media-facilitated community development in Rivers State. First, the confirmed central role of mass media in community development — through agenda-setting, opinion leader mobilisation, and framing — validates the theoretical predictions of Participatory Communication Theory

(Quebral, 2001). Media organisations that consistently foreground community issues, amplify grassroots voices, and hold government accountable serve as indispensable partners in the community development ecosystem.

Second, the finding that community-based stakeholders are generally incorporated in project planning and implementation, yet inconsistently so, highlights a critical governance gap. Stakeholders Theory (Carroll, 1991; Laetitia & Amolo, 2025) predicts that exclusion of relevant stakeholders from development processes undermines project legitimacy and sustainability. The community leader's testimony from Eligbolo confirms this: selective consultation — occurring only at advanced project stages — diminishes community ownership and can fuel conflict. This is particularly salient in a context like Rivers State, where ethnic diversity and community resource control are politically sensitive.

Third, the significant challenge posed by media ownership patterns (WMS = 3.7) deserves particular attention. In contexts where media ownership is concentrated in political and economic elites, the media's ability to serve as an impartial advocate for rural communities is structurally compromised. This finding corroborates Okhegwae et al. (2018), who found that Nigerian newspapers disproportionately covered national over community stories. The implication is that structural media reforms — including community radio licensing, local content mandates, and media pluralism policies — are necessary complements to stakeholder engagement strategies.

Finally, the strong affirmation of social media's role in community mobilisation reflects a broader global trend documented by Mzizi and Govender (2024) and Vinay (2022). In Rivers State, social media has effectively transcended geographical barriers, enabling members of rural communities — including those in other states and in the diaspora — to participate in hometown development initiatives. This digital dimension of stakeholder engagement represents a significant opportunity that development practitioners, government agencies, and non-governmental organisations must systematically incorporate into their community development frameworks.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study has demonstrated that mass media occupy a pivotal position in driving community development through stakeholders' engagement in Rivers State. Traditional media channels — radio, television, and newspapers — continue to serve advocacy functions, while new media platforms, particularly social media, have emerged as transformative tools for community mobilisation, project planning, and government accountability. The study confirms that stakeholder engagement, though practised, remains inconsistent and is constrained by illiteracy, media ownership patterns, and the selective application of participatory principles.

Based on these findings, the following recommendations are advanced. Community-based projects should be systematically prioritised in media programming schedules, with editors and broadcast managers mandated to allocate dedicated airtime and column space to grassroots development stories. Government agencies and development partners should adopt a mandatory stakeholder consultation protocol at all stages of community project cycles — from conception through execution to monitoring and evaluation — to institutionalise meaningful participation. Media regulatory authorities should enforce community ownership provisions and local content regulations, particularly for broadcast media, to counteract the urban-centric bias identified in this study. Given the demonstrated efficacy of social media in community mobilisation, digital literacy programmes should be embedded in community development initiatives in Rivers State to ensure that rural stakeholders can participate effectively in digital advocacy and project monitoring platforms. Finally, future research should explore gender-differentiated patterns of media engagement and stakeholder participation in Rivers State's community development landscape, as well as the specific impact of diaspora-driven digital advocacy on project outcomes.

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